

FAIRes Kulturerbe mit dem Smartphone und SfM?

Wie man das durch Smartphone Apps, Open Source Tools und semantische Annotation im Wikiversum und OSM erreichen kann

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3D Tage | 2025 | 04-05 Feb 2025 | Oldenburg | Germany |

04/02/2025

Themenblock: Kulturerbe

Research Squirrel Engineers Network

DOI [10.5281/zenodo.14789260](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14789260)

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FAIR

FINDABLE

ACCESSIBLE

INTEROPERABLE

REUSABLE

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via <https://5stardata.info/> and <https://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData.html>

Nachhaltige, nachvollziehbare, kollaborative (3D-)Erfassung und FAIRifizierung wird in der Citizen Science Community immer wichtiger.

2007

2008

2009

2010

2011

2017

2018

2019

2020

2023

Florian Thieri, based on lod-cloud.net, CC BY 4.0, via [Wikimedia Commons](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:LOD_Cloud_2023)

Ziel ist eine verknüpfte *Linked Open Data Cloud* in der Kulturerbe-Daten (auch 3D) auffindbar und offen sind.

Das Wikiversum und Wikibase Instanzen sind Teil der LOD Cloud

NFDI Humanities MoU Group, CC BY 4.0

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Diese Strukturen sind auch eingebunden in die NFDI

Wikimedia Foundation, CC BY-SA 3.0

WIKIBASE

WIKIBASE
CLOUD

Sketchfab

Zentral sind hier Community-Hubs und kollaborative Plattformen

KIRI Engine

Auch die digitale low-cost Erfassung mit Structure from Motion (SfM) Technologien ist mit dem Smartphone auch für nicht Geodäten möglich.

Vor mehr als 10 Jahren gab es noch 123DCATCH...

Gipsfigur und SfM mit 123DCATCH

3D-Modell berechnet mit KIRI engine
Vertices: 241'363 | Faces 482'116

Vertices x 5 !

3D-Modell berechnet mit 123Dcatch
Vertices: 46'097 | Faces 92'205

Vergleich nach ca. 10 Jahren mit AI-Unterstützung

OSM FOR HISTORY BUFFS

exploring irish history

Anne-Karoline Distel

@OSM4HistoryBuffs · 872 Abonnenten · 244 Videos

Das Hauptaugenmerk dieses Kanals sind Tutorials zum Kartografieren

[facebook.com/OSMForHistoryBuffs](https://www.facebook.com/OSMForHistoryBuffs)

Abonniert

<https://www.youtube.com/@OSM4HistoryBuffs/videos>

https://youtu.be/4SewzmdxsVo?si=RyX3t_DDzyVTuxDw
<https://youtu.be/D5I3Ck2ksTc?si=We71NuAJtaRAYgRi>

Validation process in the Task Manager for osmIRL buildings
93 Aufrufe · vor 9 Monaten

Exploring and mapping pavement lights
605 Aufrufe · vor 9 Monaten

KiriEngine: Tipps und Tricks
74 Aufrufe · vor 9 Monaten

Creating Photogrammetry Models and Uploading them to Sketchfab
461 Aufrufe · vor 10 Monaten

Sketchfab-Links zu OpenStreetMap hinzufügen
72 Aufrufe · vor 10 Monaten

Stiefelabstreifanten kartografieren
203 Aufrufe · vor 10 Monaten

KIRI Tutorials mit Anne-Karoline

KIRI Engine

Beispiel Milestone Maudlin Street

b-unicycling, CC BY 4.0, via <https://skfb.ly/oM6T7>

A-K. D., CC0, via Wikimedia Commons

via <https://www.openstreetmap.org/node/8912202795>

Knoten: 8912202795 ✕

Version #5

changed url:sketchfab to short link

Bearbeitet vor 11 Monaten von b-unicycling

Änderungssatz #143013535

Standort: 52.6525592, -7.2442662

Tags

historic	milestone
inscription	57
url:sketchfab	https://skfb.ly/oM6T7
wikimedia_commons	File:Maudlin_St_milestone.png

Milestone Maudlin Street (Kilkenny) in Sketchfab & OSM

image: Florian Thiery CC BY 4.0, created using OpenAI's DALL·E

<https://squirrelbase.wikibase.cloud>

via <https://squirrelbase.wikibase.cloud/entity/Q22>

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- In other languages
- [Add links](#)

Item Discussion

Milestone Maudlin Street (Kilkenny) (Q22)

object

[► In more languages](#)

Statements

instance of Object
 ▼ 0 references

Sketchfab URL https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/milestone-maudlin-street-eda2c0ce42104a47b88b82b70e7297b8
 ▼ 0 references

OSM ID node/8912202795
 ▼ 0 references

geometry 52°39′9″N 7°14′39.3583″W
 ▼ 0 references

via <https://tjp.de/Oale3>

item	itemLabel	geo
Q23	Alderstein Grenzstein (Aachen)	Point(6.0187331 50.7617299)
Q4	Asymmetrische Vase (Berlin Kurdamms)	Point(13.3249878 52.5026745)
Q25	Alderstein in Vaals (Niederlande)	Point(6.0187331 50.7617299)
Q6	Rom Capitol Kopf Konstantin	Point(12.4823341 49.2906206)
Q7	Rom Capitol Hand Konstantin	Point(12.4823388 41.892906111)
Q8	Rom Capitol Fuß Konstantin	Point(12.4823388 41.892906111)
Q9	Berliner Siegessäule (Mosaik)	Point(13.300108 52.514512)
Q10	Der "Große Sitzender" (Dom Würzburg)	Point(9.9318653 49.7936363)
Q11	Gedenkstein von Kurtarst Karl (Schloss Heidesberg)	Point(8.714044 49.410568)
Q12	Vater Rhein (Schloss Heidesberg)	Point(8.7191369 49.4102478)
Q13	Domnagel (Speyer)	Point(8.441199 49.317267)
Q14	Geißbrunnen (Deidesheim)	Point(8.190597 49.407566)
Q15	Köln Hohenzollernbrücke (Schlosser)	Point(6.965944 50.941421)
Q16	Statua del Mendicante di Anterselva	Point(12.1679203 46.6825371)
Q22	Milestone Maudlin Street (Kilkenny)	Point(-7.2442662 52.6525992)
Q23	CIC 153	Point(-9.6430769 52.2786287)

Die **Squirrel Base** kann diese Objekte FAIR zur Verfügung stellen

Ogham Stones

3D-Modelle in der LOD Cloud

R.A.S. Macalister, *Corpus inscriptionum insularum Celticarum*, vol. I (1945) / p.502

4.-6. AD early Medieval “Primitive Irish”

Al-qamar / CC BY-SA 3.0 via Wikimedia Commons

Ogham!

Ogham in 3D+

Digitisation, digital epigraphy and cross-sector collaboration in the study of ogham

Nora White · Early Irish MU

DIAS
Institiúid Ard-Léinn | Dublin Institute for
Bhaile Átha Cliath | Advanced Studies

 The Discovery Programme
Centre for Archaeology and Innovation Ireland

 An Roinn Cultúir,
Oidhreacht agus Gaeltachta
Department of Culture,
Heritage and the Gaeltacht

OGHAM IN 3D

museum
National Museum of Ireland
Ard-Mhúsaem na hÉireann

<https://ogham.celt.dias.ie>

Das Ogham in 3D und OG(H)AM Projekt scannt Ogham Steine ...

Encoded in XML Following EpiDoc guidelines Subset of Text Encoding Initiative


```

<asc>
<ortDesc>
<support>
<p>National Monuments Service Record Number: <ref targets="https://maps.archaeology.ie/HistoricEnvir
<material ref="materials.xml#stone">Stone</material> <objectType ref="objects.xml#mon">pillar<
described by <ref source="#MAC1945">Macalister (1945, 5)</ref> as <q>grit</q>
<dimensions unit="m" source="https://maps.archaeology.ie/HistoricEnvironment/?SNRS=MA093-0380
<height>1.80</height>
<width>0.50</width>
<depth>0.35</depth>
</dimensions>. The stone<q> has a rectangular cross-section, straight sides which taper at th
</ortDesc>
<layout>As the stone is currently leaning to an almost horizontal position, <q>the ogham inscription is
the stone, formerly the E face when the stone was vertical.</q> (<ref source="https://maps.archaeology
The inscription is <rs type="execution" key="pocked" ref="https://www.eagle-network.eu/voc/writing/lo
AVI (except the distal ends of the V) and parts of some other scores are chipped away : a flake about
broken off. The space available does not confirm Rhys's contention that the second word should be AVE
</support>
</asc>

```

Diplomatic:

Interpretive: ALATTOS MAQI BR[...]

```

<div type="edition" xml:space="preserve" xml:lang="ggl" resp="#AW">
<ab>
<lb n="1" style="text-direction:up"/>
<persName><name nymRef="#ALLATUS" corresp="http://www.dil.ie/2930">AL<unclear reason=
<w lemma="MAQAS" type="patronym" corresp="http://www.dil.ie/31166">MAQI</w>
<persName><name>BR<gap reason="lost" extent="unknown"/></name></persName>
</ab>
</div>

```


<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/ma073-012-kilmovee-371f70c582cb45c295bec7263c41bc38>

... mit SfM und SLPS und FAIRer Dokumentation mit TEI EpiDoc.

The extended Open Ogham Data Workflow!

SfM-Kampagne mit der KIRI Engine App

F. Thiery, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

F. Thiery, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

F. Thiery, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

UCC Stone #1 / CIIC 103 in KIRI ENGINE

F. Thiery, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

A.K. Distel, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0, via <https://skfb.ly/oVMpr>

Cork: Ogham Stone CIIC 89/ UCC 7

3D Model

b-unicycling

FOLLOWING

[Download 3D Model](#) + Add To </> Embed ↗ Share

◀ Triangles: **1.6M** ✓ Vertices: **812.8k** [More model information](#)

Ogham stone with no. 7 in the UCC collection, exhibited in the Stone Corridor at University College Cork.

Wikidata: [Q70885690](#)

SMR no.: CO074-164—

Made in KiriEngine from 82 photos.

Ogham Steine in Meshlab und Sketchfab

Ogham Stone GEARS/1 im Cork Public Museum

via http://archaeosquirrels.cloud/?model=CHUIS_1

via http://archaeosquirrels.cloud/?model=GEARS_1

Ogham Stones **GEARS/1** und **CHUIS/1** in 3DHOP
via archaeosquirrels.cloud

CIIC 81

- **UCC Cork Stone Corridor: #4**
- **OSM Node: 11071361392**
- **Wikidata: Q130529871**

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

Florian Thieri, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

Knoten: CIIC 81 /
UCC 4 (11071361392)

Version #2

added metadata

Bearbeitet vor 19 Tagen von fthierjgo

Änderungssatz #139090380

Standort: 51.8938126, -8.4921198

Tags

historic	ogham_stone
inscription	C[A]J[S]I[T]T[A]O]S MAQI MU[CO]I CALLITI
moved	yes
moved_to	Q69379477
name	CIIC 81 / UCC 4
project	ogham.link
source	survey
wikidata	Q106680733

Cork: Ogham stone CIIC 81/ UCC 4
3D Model

👇 1 🗨️ 5 ⭐ 0

IN COLLECTIONS

 ogham stones
b-unicycling
👁️ 13 🗨️ 0

SUGGESTED 3D MODELS

 Cork: Ogham stone CIIC 128/ UCC 25
b-unicycling
👁️ 5 🗨️ 0 ⭐ 1

 Cork: Ogham stone UCC 12/ CIIC 262
b-unicycling
👁️ 6 🗨️ 0 ⭐ 0

 Cork: Ogham stone CIIC 127/ UCC 20
b-unicycling
👁️ 6 🗨️ 0 ⭐ 0

 Cork: Ogham Stone CIIC 89/ UCC 7
b-unicycling
👁️ 12 🗨️ 0 ⭐ 0

 Cork: Ogham stone CIIC 93/ UCC 8
b-unicycling
👁️ 10 🗨️ 0 ⭐ 0

 Cork: Ogham stone CIIC 61/ UCC 24
b-unicycling
👁️ 3 🗨️ 0 ⭐ 0

LOAD MORE

UCC Ogham Stone #4 in Sketchfab

UCC Ogham Stone #4 in 3DHOP via archaeosquirrels.cloud

Use each LOD/ Wikibase-Instance for data it is “famous” for

- *Linked Open Ogham Data*: providing the primary URI
 - <https://t1p.de/3xqti>
- *fuzzy-sl Wikibase*: coordinates and how they are created
 - [P4](#)
- *Wikidata*: data-hub for external identifiers, e.g., OSM, SMRS, LOD
 - [P11693](#), [P4057](#), [P2888](#)
- *Semantic Kompakkt Wikibase*: 3D Model & Annotations
 - [P74](#), [P75](#)
- *FactGrid Wikibase for Historians*: Inscription & Persons & Words
 - [P1219](#), [P33](#), [P256](#)

Create domain-specific Wikibases!

via <https://www.istor.org/stable/25505959>

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL; <https://www.openstreetmap.org/relation/6168494>

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL;
<https://www.openstreetmap.org/way/56702954>

alt_name	Garranes Ringfort
archaeological_site	fortification
fortification_type	ringfort
historic	archaeological_site
historic:civilization	celtic
name	Lisnacaheragh Ringfort

Rath called
Lisheenagreine
ca. 51.81655, -8.76587

Florian Thiery, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

Past: CIIC 81 at the original? findspot in Garranes (Lisheenagreine)

Florian Thery, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

Today: Looking at the UCC Stone corridor

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In other languages
Add links

Item Discussion

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV (Q74)

Ogham Stone #4 UCC Stone Corridor at UCC Cork

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
British English	No label defined	No description defined	
English	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	Ogham Stone #4 UCC Stone Corridor at UCC Cork	

Statements

instance of	 Archaeological Site
	▼ 0 references

related to	 http://wikidata.org/entity/Q130529871
	related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch
	▼ 0 references

related to	 https://wikibase.semantic-kompakt.de/entity/Q1247
	related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch
	▼ 0 references

related to	 https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q1000294
	related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch
	▼ 0 references

related to	 http://lod.ogham.link/data/Y50000081
	related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch
	▼ 0 references

via <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Item:Q74>

Florian Thiery, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

fuzzy-sl Wikibase [Q74]

51°48'59.58"N, 8°45'57.13"W

certainty level Low

certainty description

Gippert/Web, Ogham 81:
 'According to Brash, JRSAI 10, 1869, 260, the stone was found in a structure called Rath Lisheenagreine, in the townland of Gurranes (sic!), parish of Templemartin, 1 mile. north of the parish church (the village in question is named "Gurranes" in the Cork U.C. too). A detailed map

of the rath (in connection with the larger Rath Lisnacaheragh) is available in S.P. O' R'Yordain's article in PRIA 47-C, 1941-42, 77 ff. - According to Brash, the stone was discovered by one farmer Crowley 17 years before (the publication of his article in JRSAI 10, 1869); Macalister states in CIIC that it "has been known since the sixties" and "appears to have come from a souterrain in the group" of "earth-works" on the townland of Gurranes. The first report was made by John Lyons, C.C., Newcestown, Enniskeane; Brash's visit took place on 16.12.1868. The stone was moved to the Museum of the U.C., Cork after Macalister first visited it (at that time it was still "standing loosely in one of the ditches". CIIC 1, 84). In the collection of the U.C., it is assigned no. 17.!

method used

acting person

source type (generic)

source type (detail)

method description

precision

location type

point type

Georeferencing

Florian Thiery

Textual Description

Paper

found in old documents

±0.0001°

Findspot

Location of a Place as a Concept

has coordinate

51°53'37.3"N, 8°29'32.6"W

certainty level

High

certainty description

on-site survey at exhibition area

method used

on-site survey

acting person

Florian Thiery

source type (detail)

on-site survey (source type)

source type (generic)

on-site survey (source type)

method description

on-site survey at UCC Cork

precision

±0.0001°

location type

Exhibition Site

point type

Exhibition

▼ 0 references

via <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Item:Q74>

fuzzy-sl Wikibase [Q74]

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Item [Discussion](#)

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV (Q130529871)

Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor

[edit](#)

CIIC 81

[In more languages](#)

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor	CIIC 81
German	No label defined	No description defined	
French	No label defined	No description defined	
Bavarian	No label defined	No description defined	

[All entered languages](#)

Statements

instance of	 ogham stone edit 0 references + add reference
	 Ogham Stone Semantic Concept edit 0 references + add reference
	 archaeological artifact edit 0 references + add reference + add value

Identifiers

FactGrid item ID Q1000294
[0 references](#)

Irish Sites and Monuments Record ID CO074-148----
[0 references](#)

OpenStreetMap node ID 11071361392
[0 references](#)

Wikidata [Q130529871]

Item [Discussion](#)

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV (Q1247)

3D model of the Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor [edit](#)

[In more languages](#)

[Configure](#)

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	3D model of the Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor	
British English	No label defined	No description defined	

[Mapping to other ontologies](#)

Predicate	URL	
		+ add mapping

Statements

instance of Media Item [edit](#)

[0 references](#) [+ add reference](#)

[+ add value](#)

license Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike [edit](#)

[0 references](#) [+ add reference](#)

[+ add value](#)

has technique Photogrammetry [edit](#)

file view

<https://semantic-kompakkt.de/entity/670e54210da6ec51ee08e5fb>

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV

3D model of the Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor

Related agents

Rightsowner: [University College Cork \(UCC\)](#)

Data Creator: [Anne-Karoline Distel](#)

Creator: [Anne-Karoline Distel](#)

Editor: [Florian Thiery](#)

Contact Person: [Florian Thiery](#)

Licence

[Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International \(CC BY-NC-SA 4.0\)](#)

Creation

Technique: [Photogrammetry](#)

Software: [KIRI engine](#)

Equipment: Smartphone

Date: Invalid Date

Related object structure

[Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV](#)

Semantic Kompakkt [Q1247]

cassittas (Q1013406)

a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Stone

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description
English	cassittas	a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Stone

CnFdI
3D DATA
ENRICHMENT

Item Discussion

C[A]SSITT[A]S Annotation (CIIC 81) (Q1255)

Person in C[A]SSITT[A]S MAQI MUCOI CALLITI

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description
English	C[A]SSITT[A]S Annotation (CIIC 81)	Person in C[A]SSITT[A]S MAQI MUCOI CALLITI

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Semantic Kompakt [Q1247]

via <https://database.factorid.de/wiki/Item:Q1000294>

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Item Discussion

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV (Q1000294)

Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor

↳ In more languages

Language	Label	Description
English	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor
British English	No label defined	No description defined

Statements

Instance of Ogham Stone
↳ 0 references

Research projects that contributed to this data set
The FactGrid Ogham Project (2024-)
↳ 0 references

Language Ogham
↳ 0 references

Genre classification Ogham Stone
↳ 0 references

Script style Ogham
↳ 0 references

inscription C[A]SSITT[A]S MAQI MUCOI CALLITI

↳ 0 references

Persons mentioned cassittas

↳ 0 references

Calliti

↳ 0 references

Things mentioned MAQI

↳ 0 references

MUCOI

↳ 0 references

cassittas (Q1013406)

a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Stone

↳ In more languages

Language	Label	Description
English	cassittas	a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Stone

Calliti (Q1013407)

a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Ston

↳ In more languages

Language	Label	Description
English	Calliti	a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Ston

MAQI (Q1013408)

son
MAQ | MAC | /-M- | MACCI | MAQCI | MACV | MACI

↳ In more languages

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	MAQI	son	MAQ MAC /-M- MACCI MAQCI MACV MACI

MUCOI (Q1013410)

túath, tribe
/-M- | MACCU | MOCU | MOCOI | MOCO

↳ In more languages

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	MUCOI	túath, tribe	/-M- MACCU MOCU MOCOI MOCO

FactGrid [Q1000294]

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryhelper Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlinken Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen: NFDI4Objects Graph --> ?item ?geo [GeoSPARQL Endpoint] Quick Add RDF Resource

Filter Concept Results:

Queryvorlagen: 10 Random Geometries Layer Name: oghamsite

Valid Query

```

1 PREFIX oghamonto: <http://ontology.ogham.link/>
2 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
3 SELECT ?item ?label ?geo ?county (count(distinct ?stone) as ?count) WHERE {
4 ?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <http://ontology.ogham.link/OghamSite> .
5 ?item rdfs:label ?label .
6 ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
7 ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
8 ?item oghamonto:within ?c .
9 ?c a oghamonto:County .
10 ?c rdfs:label ?county .
11 ?stone oghamonto:disclosedAt ?item .
12 ?stone a oghamonto:OghamStone_CIIC .
13 } GROUP BY ?item ?label ?geo ?county ORDER BY DESC(?count)

```

GeoConcepts (23)

- AnnotatedThing
- Barony
- County
- Discovery Site (DiscoverySite)
- GeographicLocation
- Island
- Klein region (KleinRegion)
- Location
- Location (Location)
- OghamSite
- Place
- ProductionCentre
- Province
- State
- Townland

<https://t1p.de/v0lgz>

Squirrel Data | Linked Open Ogham | powered by the Research Squirrel Engineers Network

Linked Ogham

#81 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project)

<http://lod.ogham.link/data/Y50000081>

The #81 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project) resource is powered by Static GeoPubby generated using the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Search: Download Options: Format: Turtle (TTL) Download

Description: comment:Ogham Stone, Ireland

Property	Value
disclosedAt (oghamonto:disclosedAt)	254000000 (xsd:G0000000)
exactMatch (oghamonto:exactMatch)	030660073 (xsd:G0660003) [L]
type (rdf:type)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> OghamStone (oghamonto:OghamStone) [L] OghamStone_Spatial (oghamonto:OghamStone_Spatial) [L] Resource (oghamonto:Resource) [L] Resource (Resource) [L]
comment (rdf:comment)	Ogham Stone, Ireland (offLang:en) (xsd:G091en)
label (rdf:label)	#81 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project) (offLang:en) (xsd:G091en)

Metadaten

Property	Value
identifier (ocid:identifier)	#1 (xsd:string)
creator (ocid:creator)	0000-0002-2044-2011 (0000-0002-2044-2011) [L]
license (ocid:license)	deed:de (deed:de) [L]
rightsHolder (ocid:rightsHolder)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 0000-0002-2044-2011 (0000-0002-2044-2011) [L] 0000-0002-4490-2000 (0000-0002-4490-2000) [L]
isAbout (ocid:isAbout)	Linked_Open_Ogham (ocid:Linked_Open_Ogham) [EN] Oghamonto:disclosedAt
wasAttributedTo (ocid:wasAttributedTo)	PythonStoneCIIC (ocid:PythonStoneCIIC)
wasDerivedFrom (ocid:wasDerivedFrom)	og_stones_en (og_stones_en) [L]
wasGeneratedBy (ocid:wasGeneratedBy)	00000000_activity (0000000000_activity)

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NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph SPARQL

geosparql:Feature
sf:MultiPolygon
sf:Point
sf:Polygon
wgs84_pos:SpatialThing

SPARQL endpoint: /api/sparql (see documentation)

```

1 PREFIX oghamonto: <http://ontology.ogham.link/>
2 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
3 SELECT ?item ?label ?geo ?county (count(distinct ?stone) as ?count) WHERE {
4 ?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <http://ontology.ogham.link/OghamSite> .
5 ?item rdfs:label ?label .
6 ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
7 ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
8 ?item oghamonto:within ?c .
9 ?c a oghamonto:County .
10 ?c rdfs:label ?county .
11 ?stone oghamonto:disclosedAt ?item .
12 ?stone a oghamonto:OghamStone_CIIC .
13 } GROUP BY ?item ?label ?geo ?county ORDER BY DESC(?count)

```

16 results

item	label	geo	county	count
<http://lod.ogham.link/ogham/OS40000031>	'Ballykeogh (Ogham Site)'	'POINT(8.071111 52.028644)'	'Cork'	11
<http://lod.ogham.link/ogham/OS40000032>	'Drumshook (Ogham Site)'	'POINT(7.648056 52.163056)'	'Waterford'	10
<http://lod.ogham.link/ogham/OS40000020>	'Bellinagaree (Ogham Site)'	'POINT(10.051111 52.12123)'	'Kerry'	9
<http://lod.ogham.link/ogham/OS40000149>	'Kilcolgaige East, Kihillcane (Ogham Site)'	'POINT(9.747222 52.071944)'	'Kerry'	9
<http://lod.ogham.link/ogham/OS40000170>	'Knockboy (Ogham Site)'	'POINT(7.6 52.111589)'	'Waterford'	8
<http://lod.ogham.link/ogham/OS40000119>	'Ballyrannig (Ogham Site)'	'POINT(10.861111 52.761111)'	'Kerry'	8
<http://lod.ogham.link/ogham/OS40000077>	'Coolnagort (Ogham Site)'	'POINT(8.642778 52.061111)'	'Kerry'	8
<http://lod.ogham.link/ogham/OS40000073>	'Coblinstown / Killen Corna (Ogham Site)'	'POINT(8.756389 53.031111)'	'Kildare'	8
<http://lod.ogham.link/ogham/OS40000039>	'Ballyhenk (Ogham Site)'	'POINT(8.608333 51.836111)'	'Kerry'	8
<http://lod.ogham.link/ogham/OS40000138>	'Knockshannagh (Ogham Site)'	'POINT(8.794722 51.868056)'	'Cork'	8
<http://lod.ogham.link/ogham/OS40000230>	'Ballyhenk (Ogham Site)'	'POINT(8.703056 52.080556)'	'Kerry'	8
<http://lod.ogham.link/ogham/OS40000154>	'Ogham Stone (Ogham Site)'	'POINT(5.649222 52.090556)'	'Waterford'	8
<http://lod.ogham.link/ogham/OS40000181>	'Maravaggin (Ogham Site)'	'POINT(8.279444 51.874444)'	'Cork'	8
<http://lod.ogham.link/ogham/OS40000208>	'Buckfield / Lahane (Ogham Site)'	'POINT(8.631667 52.028889)'	'Cork'	8
<http://lod.ogham.link/ogham/OS40000209>	'Boone More (Ogham Site)'	'POINT(7.874167 51.886667)'	'Cork'	8

LOD Ressource als "Hub-Concept" im N4O Knowledge Graph ...

... und Abfrage mit dem SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin.

Wikibase / Query Service Examples

Query Helper Filter

object of representation file view wikidata id

Limit

[Query source](#)

```

1 PREFIX wd: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/>
2 PREFIX wdt: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/direct/>
3 PREFIX wdqs: <https://query.wikidata.org/sparql>
4
5 SELECT DISTINCT ?CIIC81Label ?3D_view ?wd_id ?OSM_id ?SMRS_id ?LOD_id ?Factgrid_id WHERE {
6   SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
7   VALUES ?CIIC81 {tib:Q1407}
8   ?Media_item tibt:P63 ?CIIC81.
9   ?Media_item tibt:P74 ?3D_view.
10  ?CIIC81 tibt:P107 ?wd_id.
11
12  BIND(IRI(CONCAT(STR(wd:), ?wd_id)) AS ?wd_item)
13
14  SERVICE wdqs: {
15    ?wd_item wdt:P11693 ?OSM_id;
16    wdt:P4057 ?SMRS_id;
17    wdt:P2888 ?LOD_id;
18    wdt:P8168 ?Factgrid_id.
19  }
20 }
21

```

1 result in 513 ms

CIIC81Label	3D_view	wd_id	OSM_id	SMRS_id	LOD_id	Factgrid_id
Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	https://semantic-kompakkt.de/entity/670e54210da6ec51ee08e5fb	Q130529871	11071361392	CO074-148----	http://lod.ogham.link/data/Y50000081	Q1000294

Federating between **Semantic Kompakkt** & **Wikidata**

Federating between *Wikidata* (external IDs), *FactGrid* (related people and inscriptions), and *fuzzy-sl* (coordinates)

```

1 PREFIX wd: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/>
2 PREFIX wdt: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/direct/>
3 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
4 PREFIX fsldw: <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/entity/>
5 PREFIX fslwdt: <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/prop/direct/>
6 PREFIX fg: <https://database.factgrid.de/entity/>
7 PREFIX fgt: <https://database.factgrid.de/prop/direct/>
8
9 SELECT ?label ?wiki ?factgrid ?fslq ?inscription ?related_personsLabels ?coordinates ?osmnode ?smrid ?uri WHERE {
10 SERVICE <https://query.wikidata.org/sparql> {
11   ?wiki wdt:P31 wd:Q2016147.
12   FILTER(?wiki rdfs:label = wd:Q130529871)
13   ?wiki rdfs:label ?label.
14   FILTER(LANG(?label) IN("en"))
15   ?wiki wdt:P8168 ?factgrid;
16   wdt:P11693 ?osmnode;
17   wdt:P4057 ?smrid;
18   wdt:P2888 ?uri.
19 }
20 SERVICE <https://database.factgrid.de/sparql> {
21   fg:Q1000294 fgt:P1219 ?inscription;
22   fgt:P33 ?related_persons;
23   fgt:P1215 ?fslq.
24   ?related_persons rdfs:label ?related_personsLabels.
25   FILTER(LANG(?related_personsLabels) IN("en"))
26 }
27 SERVICE <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/query/sparql> { fsldw:Q74 fsldw:P4 ?coordinates. }
28 }

```

<https://sparql.dblp.org/YKlrP3>

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

Query results:

2 lines found 11ms in total 11ms for computation 0.0ms for resolving and sending

	?label	?wiki	?factgrid	?fslq	?inscription	?related_personsLabels	?coordinates	?osmnode	?smrid	?uri
1	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	Q130529871	Q1000294	Q74	C[À]SSITT[À]S MAQI MUCOI CALLITI	caslittas	Point(-8.492443111 51.893659305)	11071361392	CO074-148----	Y50000081
2	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	Q130529871	Q1000294	Q74	C[À]SSITT[À]S MAQI MUCOI CALLITI	Calliti	Point(-8.492443111 51.893659305)	11071361392	CO074-148----	Y50000081

Irish Holy Wells

3D-Modelle von Citizen Scientists

via <https://wiki/AQ2F>

via <https://wiki/AQ2F>

via https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:WikiProject_HolyWells

Wikidata:WikiProject Holy Wells

Holy Wells in Ireland

ID	Name	Description
Q1111111	St. Ludo's Well	...
Q1111112	St. Ludo's Well	...
Q1111113	St. Ludo's Well	...
Q1111114	St. Ludo's Well	...
Q1111115	St. Ludo's Well	...
Q1111116	St. Ludo's Well	...
Q1111117	St. Ludo's Well	...
Q1111118	St. Ludo's Well	...
Q1111119	St. Ludo's Well	...
Q1111120	St. Ludo's Well	...
Q1111121	St. Ludo's Well	...
Q1111122	St. Ludo's Well	...
Q1111123	St. Ludo's Well	...
Q1111124	St. Ludo's Well	...
Q1111125	St. Ludo's Well	...
Q1111126	St. Ludo's Well	...
Q1111127	St. Ludo's Well	...
Q1111128	St. Ludo's Well	...
Q1111129	St. Ludo's Well	...
Q1111130	St. Ludo's Well	...
Q1111131	St. Ludo's Well	...
Q1111132	St. Ludo's Well	...
Q1111133	St. Ludo's Well	...
Q1111134	St. Ludo's Well	...
Q1111135	St. Ludo's Well	...
Q1111136	St. Ludo's Well	...
Q1111137	St. Ludo's Well	...
Q1111138	St. Ludo's Well	...
Q1111139	St. Ludo's Well	...
Q1111140	St. Ludo's Well	...

The Citizen Science Wikidata Project Holy Wells

The Open Holy Wells Workflow!

Table - 🔍 25 Ergebnisse in 1876 ms </> Code 📄 Herunter

item	ItemLabel	img	geo	osm	ed
Q:121842432	Saint Fiachra's Well		Point(-7.1978959 52.6216672)	8515265450	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/sheastown-st-fiachres-well-low-poly-be3bcd3a3204744a33b2255465028b8>
Q:126448724	Our Lady's Well		Point(-7.4730101 52.7209032)	8517818852	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/clomanagh-lobermurry-02f4d7554c604a8b8665ea1bc00f9fd>
Q:126649228	Lacken Well		Point(-7.2775479 52.5438145)	9886802295	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/garrynamann-lower-lacken-well-d5be9cc7adb4b248c1bb6c2ec542582>
Q:126487120	St Coleman's Well		Point(-7.2869104 52.7352502)	998532219	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/jenkinson-st-colmans-well-low-poly-fae5988530c648aea73cfd09663954a0>
Q:122258894	Saint Fiacre's Well		Point(-6.9330041 52.5808599)	8512180854	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/ullard-st-fiachras-well-low-poly-635f79e64b434a6ea08672629b493d>
Q:122304309	Saint Molin's Well (Mullennakill)		Point(-7.11584 52.4307541)	8526433151	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/st-molings-well-low-poly-dcfff49b2f34d348d5cade4f869ad33>
Q:126456441	Columbkille's Well		Point(-7.0681791 52.4892388)	8513597500	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/inistioge-st-columbkills-well-low-poly-b0845424e49d40cfa4f0437c698ac7f5>
Q:126454844	Lady's Well		Point(-6.9566958 52.5411618)	8513574146	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/grauguenamanagh-ladys-well-9ed7bcf22e184897a5b8e758cf7249e>
Q:114439798	Kenny's Well		Point(-7.26219 52.65325)	1158290017	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/kennys-well-indoors-low-poly-685c7b9d3b0e4ba09e22263342cfc3>
Q:126458702	St. Nicholas's Well (Killamery)		Point(-7.4459883 52.4752746)	6167966637	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/killamery-st-nicholas-well-low-poly-0eeb400854164819afc5bae58dff8da>
Q:126456487	Well of the Festival		Point(-7.1257749 52.4660232)	8518908237	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/powerswood-tobernaliha-ee33390870b4d9886a0bb3c42029df69>
Q:126456487	Well of the Festival		Point(-7.1257749 52.4660232)	8518908237	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/powerswood-tobernaliha-ee33390870b4d9886a0bb3c42029df69>
Q:129263926	Holy Well		Point(-7.1637296 52.5134682)	7673751375	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/newtown-jeipoint-st-nicholas-well-62521654a1ec40c7430ccbf448869>
Q:126374490	Trinity Well		Point(-7.2710769 52.7262158)	11942593399	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/ballyraffon-trinity-well-553073f9100040e789890d3edd3cd851>
Q:122302608	St. Kieran's Well		Point(-7.3800887 52.3975027)	10544065862	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/whitechurch-kilkieran-st-kierans-well-8cdea3b21314508eb7b69faca418d76>
Q:121840779	St. Lachtain's Well		Point(-7.38951 52.7316)		<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/freshford-st-lachtains-well-low-poly-ae1ef14daa74d33bb076407134e81e>
Q:122258906	Lady's Well		Point(-7.0093773 52.6293381)	8513439301	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/goresbridge-ladys-well-status-low-poly-b6dctfdcece3e4f6ab15a3ad6550c2d18>
Q:122258906	Lady's Well		Point(-7.0093773 52.6293381)	8513439301	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/goresbridge-ladys-well-status-low-poly-b6dctfdcece3e4f6ab15a3ad6550c2d18>
Q:122258906	Lady's Well		Point(-7.0093773 52.6293381)	8513439301	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/goresbridge-ladys-well-status-low-poly-b6dctfdcece3e4f6ab15a3ad6550c2d18>
Q:122189562	Saint Augustine's Well		Point(-7.38765 52.54522)		<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/callan-st-augustines-well-low-poly-9feacac0fda14a189a1a59d2e123b1e4>
Q:126456468	Holy Cross well		Point(-7.0437511 52.4878257)	8514375323	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/kilcross-holy-cross-well-low-poly-ca1655580c28429392b1a06491333148>
Q:126657210	St. David's Well		Point(-7.2979334 52.6195581)	12144739129	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/castleinch-st-davids-well-4b6eae78a6cc43c2aee79bb6ab7c69a8>
Q:126918993	Kilkeasy Holy Well		Point(-7.2246427 52.4410735)	12015630647	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/kilkeasy-holy-well-67a39daeb3c54539a8a3147ecb29f367>
Q:126487358	St Brigid's Well		Point(-7.3565632 52.6115585)	8517798092	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/toberbreedia-st-brigids-well-56e71b0735fc4f17bdf3e84c5b2a12a7>
Q:126454422	St Leonard's Well		Point(-7.2955635 52.5006254)	7412516778	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/st-leonards-well-c6e89f2e2ae147ba90553a3a16fda690>

Holy Wells mit Sketchfab Links zu 3D-Modellen (01.02.2025)

b-unicycling, CC BY 4.0, via <https://skfb.ly/oWvIB>

Anne-Karoline Distel, CC0, via Wikimedia Commons

Freshford: St Lachtain's Well

via <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q121840779>

Wikidata

Toberlachtain (Q121840779)

Holy well dedicated to St. Lachtain near Freshford, Co. Kilderry

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Toberlachtain	Holy well dedicated to St. Lachtain near Freshford, Co. Kilderry	Tober Lachtain St. Lachtain's Well Toberlaghtain
German	No label defined	No description defined	
Russian	No label defined	No description defined	
Arabic	No label defined	No description defined	

Statements

- instance of
 - holy well (1 reference)
 - Holy Well Semantic Concept (1 reference)
- spring (1 reference)
- holy well (1 reference)
- area of use
 - abandonment (1 reference)

Identifiers

- Irish Sites and Monuments Record ID**: KK013-025---- (1 reference)
- OpenStreetMap way ID**: 935503837 (0 references)

OpenStreetMap | Bearbeiten | Chronik | Export

Suchen:

Weg: Saint Lachtain's Well (935503837)
Version #7
added sketchfab link

Bearbeitet vor 3 Monaten von bruncycling
Änderungssatz #152597977

Tags

alt_name	Toberlachtain
amenity	place_of_worship
check_date	2023-08-25
denomination	roman_catholic
description	Walled enclosure with wrought iron gate. Stone paved ground with subterranean water basin which is covered in water lenses.
name	Toberlaghtain
name:en	Saint Lachtain's Well
name:etymological:en	Q18674069
name:ga	Tober Lachtain
natural	spring
place_of_worship	holy_well
ref:en:en	KK013-025
religion	christian
source	British War Office mapsurvey

via <https://www.openstreetmap.org/way/935503837>

Freshford: St Lachtain's Well

Q28

Anne-Karoline Distel, CC BY-SA 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

Killamery: St Nicholas's Well

St. Nicholas's Well (Q126458702)

holy well in Killamery, Co. Kilkenny
 Saint Nicholas's Well (Tubberanemiscuagh)

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	St. Nicholas's Well	holy well in Killamery, Co. Kilkenny	Saint Nicholas's Well Tubberanemiscuagh
German	No label defined	No description defined	
Italian	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	

Statements

instance of

- holy well (+ 4 references)
- Holy Well Bannitic Concast (+ 0 references)

image

St Nicholas's Well, Killamery.jpg
 4,528 × 2,916 (439 KB)
 (+ 0 references)

named after

- Saint Nicholas (+ 0 references)

country

- Ireland (+ 0 references)

located in the administrative territorial entity

- County Kilkenny (+ 0 references)
- Killamery (+ 0 references)
- Kilkenny (+ 0 references)

subclass

- Roman Catholic Diocese of Ossory (+ 0 references)

Identifiers

Irish Sites and Monuments Record ID

KK030-008007-
▶ 1 reference

OpenStreetMap node ID

6167966637
▼ 0 references

OpenStreetMap Bearbeiten Chronik Export

Suchen

Knoten: Saint Nicholas's Well (6167966637)

Version #13
 added wikidata to #holy well

Bearbeitet vor 3 Monaten von b-unicycling
 Änderungssatz #152518873
 Standort: 52.4752746, -7.4459883

Tags

denomination	roman_catholic
description	Stone lined water basin of c.1m width with a large carved stone marking the spot. Water is covered in water lilies.
drinking_water	no
man_made	water_well
mapillary	75950952563297
name	Saint Nicholas's Well
names	Saint Nicholas's Well
nameatymologywikidata	Q44269
namega	Tobar San Níolas
natural	spring
place_of_worship	holy_well
pump	no
ref:esmr	KK030-008007
religion	christian

Killamery: St Nicholas's Well

Mullennakill: St Moling's Well

via <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q122304309>

Wikidata Item: **Saint Molin's Well** (Q122304309)

holy well in Mullennakill, Co. Kilkenny

Saint Moling's Well | St. Molin's Well | St. Molin's Well | Tabernamhulliang | Well of St. Molin's Tree | St. Moling's Well | St. Moling's Well

→ 31 more languages

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Saint Molin's Well	holy well in Mullennakill, Co. Kilkenny	Saint Moling's Well St. Molin's Well St. Molin's Well Tabernamhulliang Well of St. Molin's Tree St. Moling's Well St. Moling's Well
German	No label defined	No description defined	
Italian	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	

All entered languages

Statements

instance of

- holy well
- + 3 references

holy well (semantic class)

- + 0 references
- + add reference

religious site

- in use
- point in time: 2024
- + 1 reference

Identifiers

Irish Sites and Monuments Record ID **KK036-012001-**

- + 1 reference

OpenStreetMap node ID **8526433151**

- + 0 references

named after

- Mo Ling
- + 0 references
- + add reference
- + add value

Images

- St. Molin's Well, Mullennakill, Co. Kilkenny - geograph - 212482.jpg (640 × 480, 152 KB)
- + 0 references

Video

- St. Moling's Well Mullennakill, Ireland - 219149-46.s. 1.022 × 1.090, 1.22 MB
- + 0 references

OpenStreetMap Bearbeiten Chronik Export

Suchen

Knoten: St. Molin's Well (8526433151)

Version #9

added details to holy well site

Rearbeit vor 19 Tagen von b-unlocking

Änderungssatz #15528577

Standort: 52.4326685, -7.1158747

Tags

alt_name	Saint Molin's Well
drinking_water	yes
name	St. Molin's Well
name:etymology:wikidata	Q4300418
name:ga	Tobar Mholann
natural	spring
place_of_worship	holy_well
ref:osm	KK036-012001
service_times	20 August
source	British war Office map:osm
subject:wikidata	Q4300418
url:sketchfab	https://skfb.ly/7Uiv
wikidata	Q122304309
wikimedia_commons	File:St Molin's Well, Mullennakill, Co. Kilkenny - geograph.org.uk - 213492.jpg

Teil von

- 1 Weg

via <https://www.openstreetmap.org/node/8526433151>

Mullennakill: St Moling's Well

via <https://w.wiki/ANSc>

Wikidata: Warum? Abfragen → hier “named after”

Ausblick: Rock Art

Linked Open Reindeers, etc.?

The Open Linked Reindeers Workflow!

Orthofotos aus Alta und OSM Karte

Fotos/Zeichnungen: Heidi Johansen und Karin Tansem, VAM, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

Item Discussion

Hjemmeluft: Ole Pedersen 11A (A-30/31) (Q130443365)

Alla Rock Art, Hjemmeluft, Ole Pedersen 11A (A30/31)

Item Discussion

Hjemmeluft: Ole Pedersen 11A (A-34/35) (Q130443350)

Alla Rock Art, Hjemmeluft, Ole Pedersen 11A (A34/35)

Main page

Ausschnitt aus Hjemmeluft, Ole Pedersen 11A, Abschnitt A

Item Discussion

Hjemmeluft: Ole Pedersen 11A (D-127) (Q131905019)

Alta Rock Art, Hjemmeluft, Ole Pedersen 11A (D 127)

Fotos/Zeichnungen: Heidi Johansen und Karin Tansem, VAM, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

Ausschnitt aus Hjemmeluft, Ole Pedersen 11A, Abschnitt D

ALTA MUSEUM World Heritage Rock Art Centre
Alta Museum Alta, Norway
FOLLOWING [share icon] 37 Followers 0 Following

SUMMARY 51 MODELS COLLECTIONS 0 LIKES

Apana Gård 13 0

Apanes 4 0

Ole Pedersen 11 0

Bergheim 9 0

Transfarelv 6 0

Bergbukten 4 0

3D-Modelle In Sketchfab

Ole Pedersen 11A in Sketchfab

via <https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/rock-art-in-south-africa-bf376e197f045188f972b5b6a4f1eda>

via <https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/rock-art-from-himmelstalund-1-r9c7b6b5c8824d83aa03b24528db892b>

via <https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/gamnes-rock-art-site-id-219046-dcd46b35b51e479bbe8feb72166b90af>

UIT Norges arkeologiske universitetsmuseum

Mehr Modelle sind verfügbar :-)

Finis! Thx!

Questions?

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DOI [10.5281/zenodo.14789260](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14789260)

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